

Original Research

The last lynx of the Apennine mountains ridge

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Abstract

Data on the presence of Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in Central and Southern Italy are unclear. We provide a comprehensive analysis of data on the presence of lynx in this area for two periods (1500-1988 and 1989-2008), combining surveys conducted by the authors and other research groups. A total of 705 signs of lynx presence have been recorded. For the period 1989-2008, the 568 signs of presence were catalogued using the SCALP system. Data were evaluated in two survey areas: an extensive survey area (AES) and an intensive survey area (AIS). A large proportion of the observations reported lynx signs across the Central Apennines in the periods from 1989 to 1993 and from 1994 to 1998. The area represented by the Abruzzo region had the largest number of observations (445; 78.35%). Only 10 observations (1.76% of the total number of signs) could be classified as certain. Results indicate the presence of the lynx in the Apennines, which must be considered sporadic and likely represent animals that have been illegally introduced or escaped from captivity areas. It is not possible to affirm the presence of the lynx, but rather, to indicate a date by which the last Apennine lynx disappeared.

Keywords

Eurasian lynx, Apennine mountains, distribution, conservation, species extinction

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Zadnji ris iz grebena Apeninskih gora

Izvleček

Podatki o prisotnosti evrazijskega risa (*Lynx lynx*) v osrednji in južni Italiji so nejasni. Predstavljamo celovito analizo podatkov o prisotnosti risa na tem območju v dveh obdobjih (1500–1988 in 1989–2008), v kateri smo združili raziskave, ki so jih opravili avtorji in druge raziskovalne skupine. Skupaj je bilo zabeleženih 705 znakov prisotnosti risa. Za obdobje 1989–2008 je bilo 568 znakov prisotnosti katalogiziranih z uporabo sistema SCALP. Podatki so bili ovrednoteni na dveh raziskovalnih območjih: obsežnem raziskovalnem območju (AES) in intenzivnem raziskovalnem območju (AIS). Velik delež opazovanj je poročal o znakih prisotnosti risa v osrednjih Apeninih v obdobjih od 1989 do 1993 in od 1994 do 1998. Območje, ki ga predstavlja regija Abruzzo, je imelo največje število opazovanj (445; 78,35 %). Le 10 opazovanj (1,76 % skupnega števila znakov) je bilo mogoče opredeliti kot gotova. Rezultati kažejo na prisotnost risa v Apeninih, ki jo je treba obravnavati kot sporadično in verjetno predstavljajo živali, ki so bile nezakonito vnesene ali pobegnile iz ujetništva. Ni mogoče potrditi prisotnosti risa, ampak le navesti datum, ko je izginil zadnji ris iz Apeninov.

Ključne besede

Evrazijski ris, Apeninsko gorovje, razširjenost, ohranjanje, izumrtje vrste

Introduction

The lynx (*Lynx lynx*) is included in Appendix II of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora) and protected by the Bern Convention (Annexe III). The Eurasian lynx is classified as Least Concern by the IUCN (Breitenmoser et al., 2015) due to its wide distribution. However, some European subpopulations are fragmented and listed as Critically Endangered or Endangered across the EU (von Arx, 2018). The presence and distribution of the lynx in the Alps and Central Europe have been extensively studied thanks to the efforts of many researchers and specific monitoring programs: SCALP (Status and Conservation of the Alpine Lynx Population), KORA (Coordinated research projects for the conservation and management of carnivores in Switzerland), the Italian Lynx Project and others. The monitored regions included Europe (Breitenmoser-Würsten & Breitenmoser, 2021; Kaczensky et al., 2024) and the entire Italian Alpine arc (Molinari, 1998; Molinari et al., 2001; 2006; 2012; Molinari-Jobin et al., 2003; 2018). Several authors have carried out a methodical monitoring study of the presence and distribution of the Eurasian lynx in the Alpine biogeographic region which, from east to west, includes Slovenia (Stanisa et al., 2001; Koren et al., 2006; Kos et al., 2012), the Austrian Alps (Huber et al., 2001; Laass et al., 2006;

Fuxjäger et al., 2012), the German Alps (Kaczensky, 1998; Wölfl and Kaczensky, 2001; Wölfl, 2006; Wölfl & Wölfl, 2011), south-western Germany (Kaphegyí et al., 2006), Liechtenstein (Fasel, 2001; 2006), the Swiss Alps (Molinari-Jobin et al., 2001; 2006; Zimmermann, 2011), the Swiss Jura mountains (Breitenmoser et al., 2007) and the French Alps (Stahl & Vandel, 2001; Marboutin et al., 2006; 2012).

These studies, along with the adoption of conservation strategies, including reintroduction (Molinari et al., 2001), have contributed to the current status of the species, as described by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010). A significant monitoring effort has also been implemented in the central Italian Apennines; however, the results have differed from those obtained in the Alps and central Europe. The presence of the lynx in the Apennines in prehistoric times has been affirmed by De Grossi Mazzorin (1998). Recent publications (Cherin et al., 2013; Ghezzi et al., 2015; Serva et al., 2025) suggest that the discovery of fossil skeletons is irrefutable evidence of the prehistoric presence of the lynx on the Italian peninsula (Rustioni et al., 1995). The presence of the lynx in Italy during the 19th century is supported by several authors (Toschi, 1968; Tassi, 1971; Eiberle, 1972; Bruno, 1990; Chazel 2005).

The present and past distribution of this species in the Apennines is unclear, and opinions vary regarding its current presence. Many authors believed that the lynx regularly

inhabited the Apennine habitats (Tassi, 1971; Bruno, 1981; Pandolfi & Giuliani, 1994; Manzi et al., 2002) at least until the early 2000s (Rondinini et al., 2013), while others have questioned the presence of the feline (Baccetti, 1973; Cagnolaro et al. 1975). Finally, some authors have even excluded its presence for a long time (Ghigi, 1917; Toschi, 1968).

Some bibliographic sources (Pavan, 1981; Minelli et al., 2002) exclude the presence of the lynx in the central-southern Apennines since the beginning of the new millennium. The numerous reports from the 1990s seem to be linked to a series of illegal releases of unknown origin (Molinari & Molinari-Jobin, 2000; Ragni, 2002; Bologna & Mingozzi, 2003; Giglio et al. 2009; Rondinini, et al. 2013). A report dating back to 2014 can be attributed to the escape of a male specimen from the Civitella Alfedena Wildlife Area (PNALM, 2014), likely the same specimen photographed and described in the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines (ISPRA, 2014). Other sources (Tassi, 1971; 2007; Bruno, 1990; Pandolfi & Giuliani, 1994; Manzi et al., 2002; Cappiello et al., 2005) suggest that some individuals survive in remote areas of the Apennines.

This study aims to identify the temporal stages of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in a specific Italian geographical area, represented by the Apennine ridge from north to south.

The work was developed along two lines: the first analysed data obtained from indirect surveys that allowed us to evaluate a significant number of reports of lynx presence in the central-southern Italian Apennines over a historical period (1500-1988). The second used a citizen science survey, which allowed us to report observations of the Eurasian lynx over a recent period (1989-2008) and in a more restricted geographical area. The analysed data provided information on the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the central and southern Apennines, on its possible distribution in the past and present and on the possible origin of the animals.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Apennines cover a third of the Italian territory from North (Liguria) to South (Calabria) with mountains reaching 2900 m above sea level. The Tyrrhenian side (west) is characterised by the Mediterranean Biogeographic Region with

temperate deciduous forests (9110) and mixed and coniferous forests (9410, 9420). The Adriatic side (east) hosts beech forests (9110, 9130, 9210), Turkey oaks (91M0), mixed formations (91F0, 91G0, 91H0, 91AA, 91E0), riparian forests (91E0*), with the possible presence of silver fir (9220) and relict species typical of the Continental Biogeographic Region. Both slopes are home to open grasslands (6410, 6510), which, together with high-altitude pastures (62A0, 6520) and agricultural land, fragment the wooded areas. The landscape is characterised by human settlements (rural or urban), mainly in the valleys, and road and rail networks.

Given the limited number of observations (137) recovered for the historical period (1500-1988) throughout Italy, these observations will be used only to hypothesise a possible population decline from South to North. Instead, all observations relating to the period 1989-2008, which indicate the presence of lynx in various Apennine districts, are considered. In light of this and the most recent reports of lynx presence in Abruzzo (Tassi 2007), study efforts have focused primarily on two areas (Figure 1).

The Extended Study Area (AES), which, excluding Abruzzo, includes the Northern Apennines (Tuscan-Emilian Apennines); the Central Apennines (Monti della Laga, Sibillini, and Majella); and the Southern Apennines (Pollino and Aspromonte). The Intensive Study Area (AIS) encompasses the Abruzzo Region and the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park (PNALM).

Data collection and type

In order to obtain useful and verifiable information necessary to determine the presence/absence of lynx across a large area and over a long historical period, lynx presence signals provided by various research groups were collected. From 1989 to 1999, fieldwork and data collection were carried out by the Gruppo Lince Italia (<https://www.comitatoparchi.it/gruppo-lince-italia/>), a group composed of several volunteers and one of the authors. From 1999 to 2002, naturalists Luc Chazel and Muriel da Ros contributed to the Gruppo Lince Italia's investigations (<https://www.slideserve.com/xalvadora/la-lince-nell-appennino-possibile-sottospecie-della-lince-euroasiatica-lynx-lynx-di-francesco-mossolin>). From 2003 to 2008, researchers at the University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) worked to optimise the data collected and refine citizen science applied to the investigation of the presence of the lynx in the Apennines (<https://www.iris.unina.it/handle/11588/121549>). The UNINA

Group continues its carnivore monitoring surveys today.

Observations from monitoring programs supported by volunteers, local governments, and wildlife conservation organisations were also considered. Data on lynx presence were collected and classified according to their source.

The reports came from:

- Directly to the authors for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx, discovery or description of carcasses; videos or images obtained from camera traps or cameras; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of lynx presence such as footprints, scratches, scat, fur, vocalisations; discovery of dens.
- From material in museums or collections for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx, discovery or description of carcasses; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of lynx presence such as vocalisations.
- From material in scientific journals or magazines for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of the presence of the lynx, such as footprints, vocalisations, scratches, droppings, fur.

Observations contributed to form a data set that was subjected to verification, organisation and analysis. Data collection was carried out as:

- Bibliographic and web searches. Historical research was based on the collection of texts and publications (scientific journals, nature bulletins, tourist and nature guides, local historiographic works, hunting magazines, local newspapers) in which the presence of the lynx is described in the geographical areas of investigation in the period 1500-1988 (137 reports) and in the period 1989-2008 (192 reports).
- Search for historical finds. The search for taxidermized finds and stuffed animals present in museums and private collections proved very difficult, but, however, contributed to the experimental investigation (1 animal).
- Interviews. Two hundred ninety interviews were conducted, obtained from the direct testimony of elderly hunters, farmers, shepherds, breeders, inhabitants of rural areas, ecotourists, park rangers, and studious individuals. At the end of the interview, a blind test was performed, which consisted of submitting to the interviewee's attention photographic tables of different species or details of animals present in the study area.
- Field observations. Information from fieldwork (signs of presence on transects, direct observations of dead or

alive animals, tracks, scratches, faecal remains or hair) carried out by the lynx group in the period 1989-1999 (24 reports) and by the French naturalists Chazel and Ros (61 reports) was used and analysed.

All observations were classified according to the system suggested in the "First Conference on the Status and Conservation of the Alpine Lynx Population" (SCALP) (Breitenmoser, 1995; 1998), as a common standardised interpretation method is needed (Molinari-Jobin et al., 2010).

The system distinguishes three levels of reliability:

- Q1. Certain Presence: objective facts, indisputable and verifiable, including subjects captured or found dead, photographs, videos.
- Q2. Probable Presence: the finding of remains of wild prey or attacks on livestock and remains of killed domestic animals, presence indicators (traces, scratches, faecal remains, hair) confirmed by qualified operators.
- Q3. Doubtful Presence: reports submitted by unqualified or unverifiable persons and deemed unreliable

Statistical analysis

Our work was able to benefit from a good sample size that allowed us to cluster the qualitative variables represented by the lynx presence signals in the two geographical areas studied into well-defined groups. The different presence signals were assigned one of the three levels of presence reliability proposed by the SCALP group (Q1-Q2-Q3). Finally, to better evaluate the trend over time of the lynx presence in the AES and AIS areas, it was decided to carry out a more in-depth analysis starting from the year 1989. The lynx presence signals were therefore divided into four periods, each consisting of 5 years (one *lustrum*): L1 1989–1993, L2 1994–1998, L3 1999–2003, L4 2004–2008. The results obtained were compared in pairs between the groups by applying the chi-square test (SPSS, 2021).

Results

A total of 705 signs of lynx presence were collected along the Apennine mountains ridge, of which 137 reports provided information regarding the lynx in a historical period (from 1500 to 1988) and 568 reports covered a recent period (1989-2008). Figure 1 shows that in historical times the presence of the lynx on the Apennine ridge was reported in ten regions of Italy (Emilia-Romagna, Marche,

Tuscany, Umbria, Abruzzo, Molise, Lazio, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria). In the more recent period (1989-2008), the reports concerned eight regions (Emilia-Romagna, Marche, Tuscany, Umbria, Abruzzo, Molise, Lazio, Calabria).

The historical sample size covered too long a period, and individual reports could not be adequately classified using the SCALP method. Therefore, data from the historical period were used to identify reports of lynx presence geographically (Figure 2), but since it did not allow for qualitatively classifying the reports, it was not used for statistical comparison with the recent data. It was therefore decided to further analyse the recent sample, which is more consistent and divisible into four statistically comparable periods.

Table 1 shows that the highest percentage of observations was recorded in a single region: Abruzzo, i.e., only in the AIS. The remaining observations refer to the seven regions that comprise the AES. Among the latter, the highest percentage of lynx presence signs was reported in Emilia-Romagna, which therefore ranks first among the AES regions for the highest number of reports. A complete summary of the data collected during the survey is reported in Table 2, which also shows the source of the observation (reported in brackets). The analysis of all available data (Table 2) for the recent period indicated that the most frequently detected sign of presence was the sighting of animals (48.59%), followed by vocalisations (13.38%), the

finding of excrement (12.50%) and footprints (11.80%).

Reports of attacks on livestock and related damage amounted to 7.75%. The findings or reporting of animals found dead amounted to 2.11%. However, reports of hair (1.76%), scratches (0.70%) and dens (0.70%) were few. Only 0.35% of the images were captured with camera traps.

Generic data analysis (Table 2) indicates that a limited number of concrete reports were recorded: 2 photos from camera traps (1 L2 and 1 L4); 2 carcasses (1 L1 and 1 L3); 12 kills (7 L1, 2 L2; 3 L3). Most of the concrete reports were made in the first three *lustra* (four five-year periods) while only one presumed appearance from a camera trap was recorded in the last *lustrum* (2004-2008). In terms of the overall number of signs, differences were detected among the *lustra* (Table 2) from L1 to L2 (24.12% vs 44.19%, $P < 0.01$). In the following *lustra*, L3 and L4, the reporting rate showed a gradual, statistically significant decrease compared to L2 (44.19% vs 25.35%, $P < 0.01$; 44.19% vs 6.34%, $P < 0.001$). No statistical differences were observed between L1 and L3. This trend was generally followed within the categories of signs considered separately. The evaluation of the lynx presence reports according to the SCALP methodology (Table 3) over the entire study area (AES + AIS) revealed a small number (1.76%) of "certain presence" signs (Q1) that would suggest the possible persistence of the feline in the Apennines. The "certain presence" signs would be

Figure 1. Comparison map of the lynx distribution study between the Extensive Study Area (AES) and the Intensive Study Area (AIS). The diagonally striped fill indicates the Extended Study Area (AES). The dark grey solid fill indicates the Intensive Study Area (AIS), which corresponds to the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park.

Slika 1. Primerjalna karta raziskave razširjenosti risa med obsežnim raziskovalnim območjem (AES) in intenzivnim raziskovalnim območjem (AIS). Diagonalno črtasto polnilo označuje obsežno raziskovalno območje (AES). Temno sivo polnilo označuje intenzivno raziskovalno območje (AIS), ki ustreza narodnemu parku Abruzzo, Lazio in Molise.

reinforced by the data classified as "probable presence" (Q2), resulting in 26.06% if the data of the four *lustra* are taken. However, the Q1 signal in L4 refers to a single image from a camera trap. The poor quality of the image, however, reduces what was stated above. The analysis of data collected throughout the Apennines (AES and AIS) over a twenty-year period highlighted that the highest number of reports occurred in L2 (n. 251). The number of signals decreased in the following ten years. This result was probably due to the intense monitoring carried out by the Italian Lynx Group in the first decade, as also suggested by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010) in the Austrian and Italian Alps. The decrease in signals recorded in L3 can be attributed to the decrease in monitoring activities provided by specialised personnel, as well as to the reduction of voluntary monitoring. Table 3 shows the trend of lynx presence signals in the four *lustra*, dividing the data into the two geographical areas and based on the level of reliability.

Table 1 indicates that most of the observations were recorded in the AIS (78.35% vs 21.65% in the AES). A similar trend (Table 3) was observed over time in both the AIS and the AES. The analysis conducted within the intensive study area indicates statistically significant differences between L2 vs L3 ($P < 0.01$); L2 vs L1 vs L4 ($P < 0.001$); L1 and L3 vs L4 ($P < 0.0001$); L1 vs L3 (NS).

On the contrary, the data from the AES indicate a similar number of signs of lynx presence in the first two *lustra*, L1 vs L2 (NS), but differences between L2 and the two subsequent five-year periods, L3 ($P < 0.01$) and L4 ($P < 0.001$); finally, L1 differs only from L4 ($P < 0.01$). In the AIS, the level of reliability of the reports of lynx presence (Table 3) was 1.57%, 26.97% and 71.46% for Q1, Q2 and Q3, respectively

($P < 0.01$). Conversely, for AES, the reliability level of the lynx presence reports was 2.44%, 22.76% and 74.80% for Q1, Q2 and Q3, respectively ($P < 0.05$).

The lynx presence signals with a "certain presence" reliability level constituted a low percentage in both study areas; these percentages increased at both the "probable presence" and "doubtful presence" reliability levels. No significant difference was calculated between the two survey areas.

The analysis of the individual *lustra* within AIS indicates a level of "certain presence" (Q1) present in three of the four *lustra* examined (L1, L2 and L3). In all *lustra*, "probable presence" (Q2) and "doubtful presence" (Q3) were reported. Level Q2 did not demonstrate significant differences between *lustra* L2 and L3. Conversely, the observations of the two central *lustra* differed from those reported in L1 and L4 ($P < 0.0001$), just as L1 differed from L4 ($P < 0.05$). Statistical comparison within the Q3 level indicated a marked difference between the percentage in L2 and the remaining *lustra* ($P < 0.001$). The percentages of Q3 signs were similar between L1 and L3 but differed from L4 ($P < 0.001$). In the AES area, the Q1 reliability level was present only in the L3 and L4 five-year periods (66.67% vs 33.33%, $P < 0.001$). As in the AIS area, the "probable presence" (Q2) and "doubtful presence" (Q3) reliability levels are present in all the periods studied. Q2 reports were more frequent in the L1 *lustrum* than in L2 and L4 ($P < 0.01$). The *lustra*, L2, L3 and L4, were not statistically different. Q3 reports had a high degree of variability between the *lustra*: L2 showed a greater number of observations than the others ($P < 0.05$), while L1 was higher than L3 and L4 ($P < 0.05$). No differences were detected between L3 and L4.

Table 1. Eurasian lynx presence signs in the Italian regions (1989-2008). Observations number and percentage.

Tabela 1. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v italijanskih regijah (1989–2008). Število opazovanj in odstotek.

Region	Observations n.	AES only %	AES+ AIS %
Emilia-Romagna	81	65.85	14.26
Lazio	24	19.51	4.22
Marche	6	4.88	1.06
Toscana	6	4.88	1.06
Molise	1	0.81	0.18
Umbria	2	1.63	0.35
Calabria	3	2.44	0.53
Total AES	123		21.65
Abruzzo (AIS)	445		78.35
Total (AES+AIS)	568		

Table 2. List of different types of recorded observations based on the five periods (L=lustra) and historical period (Time 0). (The source of the observation is reported in brackets.)

Tabela 2. Seznam različnih vrst zabeleženih opazovanj na podlagi petih obdobj (L = lustra) in zgodovinskega obdobja (čas 0). (Vir opazovanja je naveden v oklepajih).

Observation type (source)	1989-1993	1994-1998	AES+ AIS %	1999-2003	2004-2008	Total 1989-2008	Total 1500-1988
	L1	L2	14.26	L3	L4	L1-L4	Time 0
Sightings (Authors)	22	66	4.22	48	14	150	31
Sightings (Museum and collections)	14	22	1.06	7	0	43	8
Sightings (Scientific journal)	26	53		0	0	79	18
Sightings (Magazine)	1	0		2	1	4	0
Attack/predation (Authors)	0	8		6	5	19	1
Attack/predation (Museum and collections)	0	1		1	0	2	2
Attack/predation (Scientific journal)	0	7		0	0	7	5
Damage (Authors)	2	0		0	0	2	1
Damage (Museum and collections)	4	0		1	0	5	0
Damage (Scientific journal)	7	2		0	0	9	2
Footprints (Authors)	3	13		11	9	36	2
Footprints (Museum and collections)	5	4		1	0	10	0
Footprints (Scientific journal)	11	10		0	0	21	2
Lynx killing (Authors)	1	1		2	0	4	32
Lynx killing (Museum and collections)	5	1		1	0	7	5
Lynx killing (Magazines)	1	0		0	0	1	0
Carcass (Authors)	0	0		1	0	1	0
Carcass (Museum and collections)	1	0		0	0	1	6
Vocalisations (Authors)	2	12		10	6	30	2
Vocalisations (Museum and collections)	1	0		1	0	2	0
Vocalisations (scientific journal)	22	22		0	0	44	1
Scratch (Authors)	1	0		0	0	1	4
Scratch (scientific journal)	3	0	1.06	0	0	3	6
Scats (Authors)	0	8	0.18	48	0	56	2
Scats (scientific journal)	1	14	0.35	0	0	15	7
Hair (Authors)	0	1	0.53	1	0	2	0
Hair (scientific journal)	4	4	21.65	0	0	8	0
Camera traps (Authors)	0	1	78.35	0	1	2	0
Den (Authors)	0	1		3	0	4	0
Total reliable signs	137	251		144	36	568	137

Table 3. Total number of signs of Eurasian lynx presence divided into the lustra (L1, L2, L3, L4) and the three levels of reliability (Q1, Q2, Q3), in the area of intensive study (AIS) and in the area of extensive study (AES).

Tabela 3. Skupno število znakov prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, razdeljenih na lustre (L1, L2, L3, L4) in tri stopnje zanesljivosti (Q1, Q2, Q3), na območju intenzivne študije (AIS) in na območju ekstenzivne študije (AES).

Area	year	1989-1993	1994-1998	1999-2003	2004-2008	Total
		L1	L2	L3	L4	
AIS	Q1	3	1	3	0	7
	Q2	16	47	52	5	120
	Q3	81	158	64	15	318
	Tot AIS	100	206	119	20	445
AES	Q1	0	0	2	1	3
	Q2	10	5	8	5	28
	Q3	27	40	15	10	92
	Tot AES	37	45	25	16	123

Discussion

The results show a different distribution of lynx presence signals in different periods and areas. It is possible that these discrepancies are due to differences in monitoring systems or habitat characteristics, a possibility also envisioned by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010). Unfortunately, the scarcity of signs of "certain presence" as well as the shy characteristics of the lynx and the large territory they need to live in, do not allow us to draw conclusions on the number of lynxes that would possibly inhabit the Apennine ridge. The signs Q1 and Q2 are reported scattered throughout the Apennines and have not provided sufficient data to hypothesise the possible origin of the animals. This result also occurs in other countries characterised by low lynx

populations (Huber et al., 2001; Laass et al., 2006). The data reported above have been translated cartographically (Figures 3 and 4).

In Figure 2, it is easily visible how the distribution of the lynx along the Apennine ridge has changed from the historical period (1500-1988) to the recent period (1989-2008).

In Figure 3, the areas where the greatest number of reports have been recorded are highlighted. Most of the reports can be attributed to a reliability level Q3 (Figure 4) and refer to seven regions. For the reliability level Q2, Figure 5 indicates the five regions in which the reports have been recorded. Finally, Figure 6 shows the three regions within which certain presences (Q1) of lynx have been reported.

Figure 2. Signs of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the Apennines. Comparison between the periods 1500-1988 and 1989-2008 (based on municipality).

Slika 2. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v Apeninih. Primerjava med obdobjema 1500–1988 in 1989–2008 (na podlagi občin).

Figure 3. Signs of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the Apennines during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Blue indicates low consistency; yellow, medium; red, high consistency.

Slika 3. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v Apeninih v obdobju 1989–2008 (na podlagi občin). Modra barva označuje nizko konsistentnost, rumena srednjo, rdeča pa visoko konsistentnost.

Figure 4. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q3 (blue from 1 to 9 reports; yellow from 10 to 34 reports; red from 35 to 56 reports).

Slika 4. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q3 (modra barva od 1 do 9 poročil; rumena barva od 10 do 34 poročil; rdeča barva od 35 do 56 poročil).

Figure 5. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q2 (blue from 1 to 3 reports; yellow from 4 to 13 reports; red from 14 to 27 reports).

Slika 5. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q2 (modra barva od 1 do 3 poročil; rumena barva od 4 do 13 poročil; rdeča barva od 14 do 27 poročil).

Figure 6. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q1 (blue from 1 report; yellow from 2 reports; red from 3 to 4 reports).

Slika 6. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q1 (modra barva: 1 poročilo; rumena barva: 2 poročili; rdeča barva: 3 do 4 poročila).

Conclusions

Our work indicates quite clearly that over the four *lustra* studied, reports of lynx presence have gradually decreased. This has proven to be true both in the extensive study area and in the intensive study area. The decrease in signs of certain presence (Q1) has been very significant and would lead one to think of the definitive disappearance of lynx in the central and southern Apennines. Certain observations, however, represent single individuals for which no evidence of reproductive activity has certainly been recorded over a period of twenty years.

Although the lynx is not an endangered species in Europe, it is not possible, now, to think of a management program for the species as has been done for other carnivores such as the wolf, which, despite re-proposing the human-animal conflict (Piscopo et al., 2021), has seen an increase in wild populations. The recovery and dispersion of large carnivore populations depend on many factors, some of which are controversial. A lynx conservation program (Serva et al., 2025) cannot ignore the presence of a non-fragmented forest as well as the presence of the main trophic resource constituted by the roe deer. If, for the first condition, there do not seem to be adequate solutions (increasing urbanisation), the current diffusion of some species, such as the roe deer and the wild boar, constantly increasing in the central Apennines (Piscopo et al., 2023) would lead us to think that the application of the lynx reintroduction models is possible. The major critical issues would therefore derive from the growing presence of human settlements in all habitats (Basille et al., 2009).

In conclusion, in the studied period, the signs of presence recorded are not sufficient to demonstrate the persistence of the feline in the Apennine ridge. Our data, in fact, suggest a possible presence of non-resident specimens and certainly not an active reproductive population. The ISPRA report of a lynx in the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines could coincide with that of the PNALM regarding the escape of a specimen from the wildlife area, which occurred more than five years after the end of our investigation. The subsequent discovery of a corpse would therefore confirm that this animal would be the last Apennine lynx.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; methodology, A.A., L.E.; software, A.A., N.P.; validation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; formal analysis, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; investigation, S.C., L.E.; resources, L.E.; data curation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; writing—original draft preparation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; writing—review and editing, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; visualization, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; supervision, N.P.; project administration, L.E.; funding acquisition, L.E.. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data of this study were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17485388>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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